

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE PROBLEMS FACED BY SPECIAL STUDENTS AND REMEDIAL MEASURES AT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DERA ISMAIL KHAN

Dr. Mashad Ali Raza^{*1}, Amanullah², Dr. Haleema Sadia³, Dr. Muhammad Ihsan⁴

^{*1}PhD Scholar, Tutor AIOU ISLAMABAD

²Amanullah SS (Statistics) Department of Education

³Primary School Head Teacher, Department of ESED, KP, Pakistan

⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

¹razamashad7@gmail.com, ²amansheikh819@gmail.com, ³haleemasadia431@gmail.com,
⁴muhammad.ihsan@uoli.edu.pk

Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Mashad Ali Raza

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the challenges of special students and the remedial measures identified in District Dera Ismail Khan's public and private secondary schools. Barriers in social and educational domains, and problems in the infrastructure and resources of contemporary educational systems, limit the educational participation of students with disabilities, and consequently the achievement of students with disabilities. A quantitative descriptive survey was employed in this study. The target population of this study comprised public and private secondary school teachers in the District of Dera Ismail Khan. The sample consisted of a total of 422, 222 public secondary school teachers, and 200 private secondary school teachers. For data collection, a structured questionnaire containing 24 items was developed and was measured using a five-point Likert scale. For data analysis, SPSS was used to compute the percentages, means, standard deviations, and t-tests. The study found that special students experience challenges from peers and teachers' negative attitudes, communication challenges, feelings of inadequacy, physical and structural barriers, difficulties in note taking, and inadequate support services. The study observed that teachers from public and private secondary schools differed in their perceptions of barriers and challenges of special students, supportive services and facilities for special students. Despite the recognition of educational rights of special students, both public and private secondary schools have inadequate supportive services and facilities for special students. The study suggests the improvement of school infrastructure, inclusion of special education services, and positive changes in the community.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Special Students, Disabilities, Remedial Measures, Secondary Education, Public Schools, Private Schools, Dera Ismail Khan

INTRODUCTION:

Many researchers, educators, and policy makers have considered inclusion. Many advocates of inclusive education integrate students with

special educational needs into mainstream schools based on humanitarian, moral, social, and educational perspectives. Peterson (2010) argued that inclusion creates opportunities for

students with disabilities to receive an education and participate in society. On the contrary, Warnock (2005) argued that inclusion in the mainstream classroom creates the possibility of untapped potential and social inclusion in the life of the school for students with special educational needs. Inclusion of special educational needs students in mainstream schools provides them with an education that is just, equitable, and compassionate. They consider that the discriminatory nature of segregated education does not assist students with special educational needs to learn and participate in their local communities. Further, the special educational needs students in segregated education in the local schools are socially invisible, and lack the dignity, self-respect, and worth that are valuable and beneficial to society (Stainback & Stainback, 1996).

The integration of special education within the general education system is becoming more recognized. However, there are still challenges pertaining to the placement of special education students in the general education system. Many students struggle to develop relationships with their teachers and peers, which has both a social and academic impact. It has been suggested that the absence of knowledge and understanding of disability may discourage teachers and may even result in negative attitudes and the provision of inappropriate education. Campbell, Dodson, and Boss (1985) suggested that because some teachers fail to understand the special needs of disabled students, the teachers may unwittingly discourage them. It has also been documented that many teachers confuse disabilities with mental illnesses and therefore, use inappropriate labels which can have a negative impact on the students. Due to the absence of professional preparation and specialized coaching, teachers often prefer to work with students who do not have disabilities. Students who have disabilities may experience low self-esteem and social exclusion, which will impede their academic progress. For the above reasons, it is very important to examine the various issues special students face and offer proper solutions that will

improve their educational placement and promote successful integration into general education.

The Main Objective of the Research study: The research had several objectives. One was to identify the special students' problems and the available remedial measures for them in the public and private secondary schools of District Dera Ismail Khan. Another was to find out the difficulties faced by special students in mainstream schools which fall in the educational, social, and communication and infrastructure domains, and the perceptions of teachers about these difficulties. This research also intended to find out the level and range of support services as well as the facilities that are made available by the public and private sectors, and to find out whether there are any significant differences between the two sectors. This study was aimed at addressing the key obstacles to including special students in the mainstream schools, as well as the remedial measures that exist, and offering realistic measures and strategies to maximize the educational, social, and inclusive measures of special students and to enhance their overall academic and personal development. To get an understanding of the perspectives of public secondary school instructors on the issues faced by special children and the unmeasured remedial services provided at the secondary level in D.I. Khan. To get an understanding of the perspectives of private secondary school instructors on the unique needs of children and the unmeasured remedial services provided at the secondary level at D.I. Khan. To gain an understanding of the services and resources available to students with special needs in public secondary schools. It is necessary to be aware of the services given by private secondary schools to kids who have special needs. The purpose of this study was to examine the differences in opinions between public and private secondary school instructors on physical facilities for impaired children hitherto unmeasured at the secondary level in D.I. Khan, and to provide recommendations.

Research Hypothesis: Alternative hypothesis of the research is:

There is a significant difference between the perceptions of public and private secondary school teachers regarding the problems faced by special students and remedial measures available at the secondary level in District Dera Ismail Khan.

Literature Review

Overview:

Concept of Inclusive Education

Inclusive education is a broad multi-faceted idea that is an area of focus for many researchers and education policymakers globally. According to Ainscow (2006), inclusion is a multi-dimensional concept that can be defined differently based on the educational systems or contexts in question. Booth and Ainscow (2002) argued that inclusive education is not restricted to children that have special educational needs; rather, it should include all learners that face challenges to learning and participating. Likewise, Dyson (1999) argued that even though the different concepts of inclusion can be diverse, the common goal is to provide all learners the chance to access education. According to Farrell (2000), inclusion should not only be the placement of children with special educational needs into the mainstream schools, but rather the focus should be on the enhancement of the children's educational experiences within the school, and on their belonging to the school.

Over the past few decades, the inclusion movement has promoted the rights of children with disabilities, and has worked to provide them with equal access to education. The final report of the Disability Rights Task Force (2004) and the Ministry of Education (2004) documented the importance of diminishing discrimination and enhancing the provision of services to assist children with special educational needs. Inclusive education is envisioned as creating learning spaces where all children can participate and benefit from education, regardless of their disabilities.

Teachers' Attitudes Toward Inclusive Education

The successful integration of inclusive education depends heavily on teachers. Heiman (2004) stated that with appropriate educational and psychological support, children with special educational needs would be able to learn within mainstream schools. On the other hand, Heiman (2002) and Priestley and Rabiee (2002) stated that teachers are concerned about the social and behavioral adjustment of students with disabilities. Many of these teachers report feeling unprepared to meet the needs of these students because of a lack of training and resources.

In relation to the inclusion of students with special educational needs, various researchers have studied the causes of attitudes of teachers. Vaughn et al (1996) stated that large class sizes, a shortage of funds, an excessive working load, and difficulties with assessment usually cause teachers to be unsupportive of inclusion. Also, Danne and Beirne-Smith (2002) reported that teachers usually request the help and the opportunity to work closely with other professionals to assist students with special educational needs. Loreman et al (2005) stated that teacher cooperation, solicitude, and willingness are a pre-requisite for successful inclusive education programs. Finally, Good and Brophy (2007) stated that even though teachers are the most important facilitators of any educational program, a favorable attitude on the part of teachers of the system is also bound to make inclusion a success.

Benefits and Challenges of Inclusive Education

The social and educational advantages of inclusive education are backed by plenty of research. Batool and Mehmood (2002) observed that children with visual impairments and their typically developing peers can hold similar opinions and successfully interact with one another in inclusive education systems. Noor and Khokhar (2002) revealed that though students with physical disabilities experienced mobility and transport problems, they appreciated the efforts of teachers and school administrators. Inclusive education systems support sustained interaction, socially and developmentally, of

children with and without disabilities (Ali et al., 2006).

Although inclusive education systems are meant to integrate children with disabilities, there are numerous challenges that still persist. For instance, many of them experience social isolation; some have inadequate access to learning materials; others face the challenge of school facilities that are not designed to cater for them; and in some cases, they have to deal with negative attitudes from their schoolmates and teachers. According to Aahmadi (2007), many children with disabilities are confined to passive participation in the few activities that are not restricted by school design. Zakarya (1995) also pointed out negative attitudes toward children with disabilities and the lack of personnel with the skills to work with children with disabilities. This has contributed to the low self-esteem and the limited social, and educational participation of children with special educational needs.

International Development of Inclusive Education

The concept of inclusive education gained international recognition through several global initiatives. The Salamanca Statement of 1994 represented a major milestone in promoting inclusive education worldwide. The conference emphasized that regular schools with inclusive orientations are the most effective means of combating discrimination, creating welcoming communities, and achieving education for all (UNESCO, 1994). The World Education Forum held in Dakar in 2000 further reinforced the commitment to providing educational opportunities for marginalized and disadvantaged groups, including individuals with disabilities.

Historically, individuals with disabilities were often excluded from educational and social participation. Tremblay (2007) and Rymer (2014) documented how people with disabilities faced discrimination and neglect in ancient societies. Over time, however, significant progress occurred through educational reforms and advocacy efforts. Pedro Ponce de Leon established one of the earliest institutions for hearing-impaired students in Spain, while Louis Braille developed

the Braille system for individuals with visual impairments. These developments laid the foundation for modern special and inclusive education systems.

Special Education and Inclusive Education in Pakistan

The creation of systems for special education in Pakistan started slowly after the country gained independence. Hameed (2003) states that in the initial years after independence there were very few educational facilities for the disabled. The first school for the blind was opened in 1906, and schools for the deaf were opened in subsequent years. The National Policy for Education and Rehabilitation of the Disabled was initiated in 1988, and its first revision was in 2002, focusing on the improvement of education and rehabilitation of persons with disabilities.

Pakistan has endorsed and participated in many international programs on inclusive education. These include the Salamanca Framework and Education for All Programs (UNICEF, 2004). In Pakistan, there are great developments in establishing special educational facilities, training teachers, and providing educational materials to disabled students. Hameed (2006) states that there are now hundreds of educational facilities for disabled students, in both the public and private sectors. Nevertheless, poor infrastructure, insufficient trained teachers, assistive technologies, and negative social attitudes are barriers to providing quality educational services.

Education of Deaf Students and Related Challenges

Bashir (2005) noted the barriers of communication and limited socialization with the hearing population leave many deaf children socially isolated. Khatoon (2003) stated that although deaf education in Pakistan cannot proceed effectively without the use of Pakistan Sign Language (PSL), many teachers do not have the necessary training. Hussain (2003) and Majeed and Saeed (1998) discuss the shortage of audiologists, speech therapists, and educators with special training and the impact this has on the deaf population in Pakistan.

Many of the difficulties faced by deaf students appear to be social and emotional, stemming from barriers to communication that result in feelings of isolation, low self-confidence, and frustration. Husain (2003) stated that individuals who are hearing-impaired remain socially isolated and lack self-confidence and that many have little or no schooling. Umar and Muhammad (2007) suggested that emotional and psychological support and articulation of communication strategies would enhance the social adjustment of

deaf students.

Research Design:

Research design is the overall plan or blueprint that guides the collection, measurement, and analysis of data to answer research questions and achieve the objectives of a study. It provides a systematic framework for conducting research in a valid and reliable manner (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The study's format was descriptive in nature.

Population of research:

The study sample consisted of all secondary school teachers, both public and private, from both public and private schools of district D I Khan.

Total public Secondary school	Total Private Secondary school	No of public-school teachers	No of private school teachers
78	50	1112	2000

Sample and Sampling Technique:

The study employed a census (complete enumeration) strategy and invited all secondary school Teachers were selected using a simple random sample approach and 10 Public and 10 private secondary schools were selected using a convenient sampling technique. When a study's overall population crosses 1.5 million people, according to Gay (1987) and Gary & Airasian (2003), the size of sample becomes almost negligible, and a sample of up to 400 is almost considered acceptable. Furthermore the sample size will be determined by the target population's homogeneity or heterogeneity. Researcher was select 222 teachers from public and 200 teachers from private secondary school.

Disagree (1), focusing on the perceptions and experiences related to inclusive education and the challenges faced by students with special needs in secondary schools.

The questionnaire covered key dimensions including accessibility and physical environment of schools, communication and classroom interaction, teacher preparedness and instructional practices, curriculum and assessment suitability, social attitudes and inclusion of peers, institutional support and policy implementation, parental involvement, and the use of assistive support such as ICT. It also examined students' emotional experiences, academic participation, and equal treatment within regular school settings. These dimensions collectively aimed to assess the extent to which secondary schools accommodate and support the educational needs of disabled students in both public and private institutions.

Instrument for Data Collection:

A structured questionnaire was developed to collect data based on the objectives and variables of the study regarding special education needs in inclusive school settings. The instrument was designed after an extensive review of relevant literature and consisted of two main sections. Part I included demographic information of the respondents such as gender, age, qualification, and teaching experience. Part II contained statements measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (5) to Strongly

Validity and Reliability of Research Instrument:

For the purpose of determining the validity and reliability of the research instrument, the questionnaire was distributed to PhD candidates as well as professionals and teachers from relevant departments.

Procedure of the Study:

Respondents completed an approved questionnaire, which was then collected by the researcher, who then conducted an analysis of their replies using the statistical technique T-test,

as advised by the supervisor, to determine what they thought.

Data analysis

Simple percentage mean standard deviation and T-test was used as a statistical technique.

Table4.4: Students with special needs feel inferiority complex in ordinary school

Options	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Public Teachers	90	115	17	0	0	222
Percentage	40.5%	51.8%	7.6%	0%	0%	100%
Private Teachers	30	140	15	15	0	200
Percentage	15%	70%	7.5%	7.5%	0%	100%

The majority of respondents i.e. public teacher were agree 92.3% and private teachers were agree 85%. Public teacher 0% and private teachers 7.5% were disagreed. Public teachers 7.6% and

private school teacher 7.5% could not decide favor or against regarding Students with special needs feel inferiority complex in ordinary school.

Table # 4.4.1: Students with special needs feel inferiority complex in ordinary school

Stakeholders	Sectors	N	Means	S.D	T _{cal}	T _{tab}	P _{value}
Teachers	Public	222	4.61	0.63	33.46	±1.96	0.01
	Private	200	2.63	0.58			

The difference in perceptions between the public and private responder is shown by the T-calculated value of 33.46 and the P-value of 0.01, respectively.

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Stakeholders	Sectors	N	Means	S.D	Tcal	Ttab	P-value
Teachers	Public	222	4.61	0.63	33.46	≠1.96	0.01
	Private	200	2.63	0.58			

The difference in perceptions between the public and private responder is shown by the T-calculated value of 33.46 and the P-value of 0.01, respectively.

Table4.9: Disabled students faced communication problems in school

Options	Strongly agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Total
Public Teachers	0	0	0	200	22	222
Percentage	0%	0%	0%	90%	9.9%	100%
Private Teachers	0	0	0	173	27	200
Percentage	%	%	%	86.5%	13.5%	100%

The majority of respondents, i.e. public school teachers, agreed with 0 percent of the responses, while private school teachers agreed with 0 percent of the responses. The majority of public school instructors and the majority of private

school teachers were in disagreement. Disabled pupils encountered communication difficulties at school, and 0 percent of public school instructors and 0 percent of private school teachers could not make a decision in favor or against them.

Table # 4.9.1: Disabled students faced communication problems in school

Stakeholders	Sectors	N	Means	S.D	T _{cal}	T _{tab}	P _{value}
Teachers	Public	222	5.57		0.29	-8.94	≠1.96
	Private	200	5.84		0.33		

The difference in perceptions between the public and private responder is shown by the T-calculated value of -8.94 and the P-value of .001, demonstrating the difference in perceptions.

Table # 4.9.1: Disabled students faced communication problems in school

The difference in perceptions between the public and private responder is shown by the T-calculated value of **-8.94** and the P-value of **.001**, demonstrating the difference in perceptions.

Discussions

The results of this research show that there are major differences between public and private secondary school teachers' perceptions of the issues that special students face in mainstream schools. In Table 4.4, a huge majority of teachers from public schools (92.3%) and private schools (85) agreed that special needs students develop inferiority complexes when placed in mainstream schools. The considerable t-value (33.46) and p-value (0.01) affirmed disparate opinions of the two sectors of teachers. It can be perceived that students with special needs are likely to develop low self-esteem, be socially alienated, and experience a sense of worthlessness and inadequacy when they are placed in a classroom with students who are not physically and mentally challenged and are provided with little or no support.

Table 4.9 provided insight into most public (99.9%) and private (100%) school respondents' opinions that disabled students do not

experience communication difficulties when they are in school. However, due to the considerable t-value of (-8.94) and p-value of (.001), a statistically considerable gap of perceptions of the two teaching groups is evident, even though the two teachers groups appear to converge in their belief that communication does not pose a major gap in assessments of special students. Results in this study suggest the need for a greater focus on the advancement of support services and the development of specialized educational services and resources to improve secondary educational systems that meet the needs of students with special educational requirements in Dera Ismail Khan.

Conclusions

According to the study, both public and private secondary school teachers view students with special needs as having an inferiority complex. Public and private secondary school teachers experience this perception with different

intensities. Public and private secondary school teachers view participating students in ordinary classes and schools as not having communication problems. The data analysis indicated differences in the perceptions of public and private secondary school teachers on the two issues. For special needs students to experience an improved sense of well-being and accommodate the educational environment in Dera Ismail Khan, inclusive educational systems, and counseling and supportive services, are needed.

Recommendations

- Counseling Services should be established at schools to help special students with developing their self-confidence as well as their feelings of inferiority.
- Allocating additional funding for students with special needs means that there will be the means to provide teachers with regular training on how to be inclusive towards students with special needs.
- Schools need to build a more positive and welcoming environment that increases student participation within classrooms.
- Educational resources and support services need to be specialized and varied to address the needs of all the special students.

References

- Aahmadi. (2007). *Barriers to inclusive education in developing countries*. Educational Review Journal.
- Ainscow, M. (2006). *Towards a more inclusive education system*. Routledge.
- Ali, A., Khan, S., & Rehman, F. (2006). Social interaction in inclusive classrooms: A study of students with disabilities. *Journal of Special Education Research*, 12(2), 45–58.
- Bashir, M. (2005). Communication barriers among deaf students in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Special Education*, 8(1), 22–31.
- Batool, R., & Mehmood, A. (2002). Inclusive education and visual impairment: A comparative study. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 5(1), 67–75.
- Booth, T., & Ainscow, M. (2002). *Index for inclusion: Developing learning and participation in schools*. Centre for Studies on Inclusive Education.
- Campbell, P., Dodson, M., & Boss, L. (1985). Teacher perceptions of students with disabilities. *Exceptional Children*, 51(4), 321–330.
- Danne, J., & Beirne-Smith, M. (2002). Collaboration in special education: Teacher perspectives. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 35(3), 210–218.
- Dyson, A. (1999). Inclusion and inclusion: The debate continues. *British Journal of Special Education*, 26(3), 140–145.
- Farrell, P. (2000). The impact of research on inclusive education. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*, 4(2), 153–162.
- Good, T. L., & Brophy, J. E. (2007). *Looking in classrooms* (10th ed.). Pearson.
- Hameed, A. (2003). Development of special education in Pakistan: A historical perspective. *Journal of Education and Development*, 3(1), 15–28.
- Hameed, A. (2006). Expansion of special education institutions in Pakistan. *Pakistan Journal of Education*, 5(2), 33–42.
- Heiman, T. (2002). Inclusive education: Teachers' concerns and expectations. *Journal of Special Education*, 36(3), 145–152.
- Heiman, T. (2004). Students with disabilities in inclusive settings: Academic and social outcomes. *International Journal of Disability Development and Education*, 51(2), 117–129.
- Hussain, S. (2003). Challenges faced by hearing-impaired students in Pakistan. *Journal of Deaf Studies*, 6(2), 40–52.
- Khatoon, S. (2003). Pakistan Sign Language and teacher training issues. *Asian Journal of Special Education*, 2(1), 55–63.
- Loreman, T., Deppeler, J., & Harvey, D. (2005). *Inclusive education: A practical guide to supporting diversity in the classroom*. Routledge.
- Majeed, R., & Saeed, M. (1998). Special education services in Pakistan: Issues and challenges. *Journal of Rehabilitation Sciences*, 4(1), 12–20.

- Ministry of Education. (2004). *National education policy review report*. Government of Pakistan.
- Noor, M., & Khokhar, A. (2002). Experiences of students with physical disabilities in inclusive schools. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(1), 88-95.
- Priestley, M., & Rabiee, P. (2002). Exploring teachers' perceptions of inclusion. *British Journal of Special Education*, 29(1), 18-24.
- Stainback, S., & Stainback, W. (1996). *Inclusion: A guide for educators*. Brookes Publishing.
- Tremblay, P. (2007). Historical perspectives on disability and education. *Disability Studies Quarterly*, 27(3), 1-12.
- UNESCO. (1994). *The Salamanca statement and framework for action on special needs education*. UNESCO.
- UNICEF. (2004). *Education for all in Pakistan: Progress report*. UNICEF Pakistan.
- Umar, F., & Muhammad, N. (2007). Emotional adjustment of hearing-impaired students. *Pakistan Journal of Psychology*, 10(2), 60-70.
- Vaughn, S., Schumm, J. S., & Kouzekanani, K. (1996). The effects of inclusion on teachers. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 29(5), 576-588.
- Waheed, A. (n.d.). Psychological issues among deaf students. *Unpublished manuscript*.
- Warnock, M. (2005). Special educational needs: A new look. *Philosophy of Education Review*, 37(2), 5-12.
- Zakarya, M. (1995). Barriers to special education in developing countries. *Asian Education Review*, 3(1), 25-34.